

MODELLING THE NON-LINEAR MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF TRIAXIAL BRAIDED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In the presented work, we propose a framework for predicting the non-linear mechanical response of triaxial braided composites using meso-scale finite element unit cells. Based on a reduced unit cell concept which exploits symmetries to minimise computational expense, a compacted and interpenetration-free yarn geometry is created within a three stage simulation process. In the first step, a nominal geometry is constructed from user-defined input parameters. Local volumetric interpenetrations present in the model are resolved in a subsequent fictitious thermal step. The unit cell is further compacted to the desired fibre volume fraction using flexible membranes. Out-of-plane periodic boundary conditions allow an implicit consideration of the compaction of multiple braid plies in different nesting configurations, which further enables us to render high global fibre volume fractions (55-60%) using experimentally determined intra-yarn fibre volume fractions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Applying new lightweight materials, such as carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) in the automotive industry allows a significant reduction in structural weight and carbon dioxide emissions. In these high-volume production industries, current manufacturing technologies face a twofold challenge: cost and cycle time. Braiding combines an automated and reproducible process together with an excellent rate of material deposition for mass-production of high performance structures. Yarns of several thousand carbon fibres are intertwined and positioned on a mandrel to produce geometries with complex cross-sections. Accurately modelling the mechanical response of 2D braided composites, however, remains a challenging task due to their textile nature, which includes out-of-plane waviness, interactions between intertwining yarns and nesting of multiple plies in the through-thickness direction.

Numerical modelling using meso-scale finite-element (FE) unit cell models provides a powerful tool to study the material behaviour of braided composites. Typically, a representative domain of the internal textile geometry is considered, wherein the constituent reinforcing yarns are explicitly modelled as solid continua. This approach can be applied to a variety of problems, ranging from determining dry fabric permeability or draping characteristics to the composite mechanical response, including accurate prediction of stress-strain fields, macroscopic mechanical properties, and the investigation of the non-linear behaviour with damage initiation and development.

The fidelity of unit cell models is largely affected by a realistic representation of the underlying textile geometry. Geometry pre-processors, such as WiseTex [1] or TexGen [2], provide good results

for a variety of textile architectures, but due to their idealised geometrical topology, they offer only limited capabilities for modelling highly compacted triaxial braided composites with global fibre volume fractions (FVFs) of 55 – 60%. Here, the non-orthogonal interlacing of three in-plane fibre directions yields a complex internal geometry. Particularly after compacting multiple layers of braid, the fabric features severely distorted yarns with multiple contact zones, locally varying intra-yarn FVF and fibre orientations.

Recently, increased research emphasis has been put on extending established textile modelling strategies [3] to more realistic geometry models [4]. Hivet and Boisse [5] developed a consistent 3D CAD formulation devoid of interpenetration for the forming simulation of 2D woven fabrics, in which contact zones between yarns are represented by shared geometrical faces. Using a hypoelastic material model for the yarns, the compaction and nesting behaviour of stacked 2D woven fabrics was investigated by Nguyen et al. [6]. In addition, Grail et al. [7] developed a mesh distortion algorithm to remove the resulting mesh inconsistency between orthogonal yarns after forming and investigated the mechanical performance of the resulting composite unit cell. Other researcher have tried to mimic the dry fabric behaviour by representing each yarn through several chains of one-dimensional finite elements in contact, thus explicitly rendering the effect of inter-fibre sliding [8, 9]. While results of the investigated 3D woven geometry agree well with computer tomography (CT) scans, a sophisticated post-processing technique is necessary to reconstruct yarn surfaces. Additionally, the multitude of contacts in the model is accompanied by high computational expense. Green et al. studied the mechanical response of the above mentioned geometry using FE voxel discretisation [10]. Significant differences between nominal and deformed geometry model were observed.

In the presented work, we propose a modelling framework for predicting the mechanical response of triaxial braided composites using FE unit cells with realistic geometry. The general procedure is derived from a list of key modelling requirements emphasised in the literature:

1. Increased computational efficiency or modelling detail by minimisation of the unit cell domain through application of in-plane periodic boundary conditions (PBCs) and consideration of nesting and compaction effects through out-of-plane PBCs.
2. Accurate representation of textile geometry and properties without unsound assumptions. This includes the correct representation of the global FVF through a realistic axial and braid intra-yarn FVF, an interpenetration-free geometry model considering yarn-to-yarn contact without over-idealisations and the capability to simulate typical failure modes encountered in triaxial braided composites.
3. High fidelity in the prediction of localised stress-strain fields with the possibility to implement typical 3D continuum damage models.
4. To solely rely on software packages widely used and available within the research community, combined with a high degree of automation through scripting for easy accessibility to other users. Throughout this work, all models were generated and solved in the unified FE package Abaqus, which was controlled by MATLAB and the corresponding Python scripting interface.

2 MODELLING FRAMEWORK

2.1 Roadmap and Dataflow

The modelling procedure is schematically shown in Fig. 1. Based on a reduced unit cell concept to minimise computational expense developed by De Carvalho et al. [11], a compacted and interpenetration-

Figure 1: Roadmap and data flow for generating a realistic unit cell model

free yarn geometry is created within a three stage simulation process. In the first step, a nominal geometry is constructed from user-defined input parameters, such as braiding angle, yarn spacing and its respective cross-sectional shape. As a result of the absence of initial contact between intertwining yarns at this stage, local volumetric interpenetrations present in the model are resolved in a subsequent fictitious thermal step, in which contact is established within the entire unit cell. In the final step, the unit cell is compacted to the desired FVF using flexible membranes. Special out-of-plane periodic boundary conditions allow an implicit consideration of the compaction of multiple braid plies in different nesting configurations, which further enables us to render global FVFs of 55 – 60% without assuming an unrealistically high FVF inside the yarns. Finally, the deformed hexahedral yarn mesh is used in a series of boolean operations to create an inconsistent tetrahedral matrix mesh, and both meshes are coupled using a cohesive contact formulation in order to investigate the mechanical behaviour of the braided composite.

2.2 Geometry Model and Meshing

In the first step of the framework, a surface mesh of the textile is generated from user-defined input parameters. Aside from geometrical data, such as braiding angle, yarn height, width, spacing and FE mesh size for braid and axial yarns, their respective intra-yarn FVF as well as the global target FVF must be defined. Initially, a constant idealised cross-section is selected for all yarns. Axial yarns are assumed to be straight, and their cross-sectional surface is described by a modified sinusoidal function:

$$z_{(a)} = \pm \frac{t_a(1 - \xi_a)}{2} \cdot \cos\left(\frac{y \cdot \pi}{w_a}\right)^{n_a} \pm \frac{\xi_a \cdot t_a}{2} \quad (1)$$

for which the geometrical parameters are displayed in Fig. 2 and the sign change indicates separate equations for the top and bottom surface. For subsequent mesh quality purposes, the cross-section can be truncated at a predefined side thickness of $\xi_a \cdot t_a$. The exponent n_a creates an adaptive cross-section, capable of mimicking a specific yarn shape or the measured average cross-sectional area, such that consistency of FVF, fibre count and diameter are achieved inside all yarns.

Figure 2: Initial geometry representation

For both the positively and negatively oriented braid yarn surfaces, an adapted formulation of the model developed for biaxial braids by Goyal et al. [12] is implemented. In the corresponding local coordinate system, the cross-sectional term is superimposed with an additional sinusoidal function responsible for the waviness of amplitude h_u :

$$z_{(b+,b-)} = \pm \frac{t_b(1-\xi_b)}{2} \cdot \cos\left(\frac{y' \cdot \pi}{w_b}\right)^{n_b} \pm \frac{\xi_b \cdot t_b}{2} + h_u \cdot \sin\left(x' - \frac{\omega_{(b+,b-)} \cdot \pi}{L_u(1-\zeta)}\right) \quad (2)$$

By incorporating a braiding angle dependent localised phase shift given by:

$$\omega_{(b+,b-)} = \pm \chi \cdot y' \cdot \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - 2 \cdot \theta\right) \cdot \cos\left(\frac{x' \cdot \pi}{L_u}\right)^2 \quad (3)$$

into the undulation term, the volumetric shape can be analytically distorted while retaining a constant cross-sectional area. A key advantage of this approach lies in the significant reduction of interpenetrations for braiding angles $\neq 45^\circ$, as can be seen for a $[0/\pm 60]$ braid in Fig. 2 with non-orthogonal yarn intersections. In addition to the linear variation in yarn transverse direction, the shift magnitude is varied quadratically along the centre line until its maximum is reached at half of the wavelength L_u . Due to the close proximity of the domains at this kinematic intersection point, the highest phase shift is introduced here. For minimised overlapping of braid and axial yarns, the distortion term vanishes at the corresponding intersection points. It is worth mentioning that a pure rotation of cross-sections, as is often performed in woven composites, has shown only limited potential for application in triaxial braids. In many cases, this procedure may reduce the interference with one entity on one side of a cross-section while causing

Figure 3: Reduced unit cell with periodic boundary conditions

a severe overlap on the other side.

From the starting point of this analytical surface description, an undulated master yarn is constructed in MATLAB through a series of blended cross-sections. Each cross-section is discretised with the user-defined FE mesh size, which will later serve as a baseline for the hexahedral unit cell mesh. Furthermore, several segments along the master yarn are extracted, assembled, and rendered in 3D space, which allows visual inspection and, if desired, a quick modification of parameters by the user.

This exported surface mesh is converted into a solid Abaqus native CAD geometry, featuring spline interpolation along the yarn path. For the transverse direction, linear interpolation is selected, which enables us to retain spatial information on predefined mesh seeds through geometric edges. Working on CAD geometry as opposed to discrete meshes provides many key benefits, such as granting access to volumetric boolean operations, which are particularly useful for unit cell modelling. Hence, with an arbitrary unit cell selected by the user, an exact CAD representation is obtained, independent of the angle of intersection between yarn entities and unit cell boundaries. The biggest advantage of the presented approach, however, lies in the resulting inherent mesh periodicity caused by the boundary cut operation. Geometric edges representing the transversal mesh seeds are cropped at the unit cell boundaries, such that a periodic structure of boundary vertices is created. These anchor points, which are coincident with nodal positions, ensure a periodic nature of the boundary discretisation during the subsequent mesh generation.

2.3 Periodic Boundary Conditions

In order to minimise computational effort, a reduced unit cell (rUC) for triaxial braided composites is derived on the basis of the equivalence framework for periodic structures developed by De Carvalho et al. [11]. In general, the periodic displacement boundary conditions for a deformable periodic body which includes symmetries can be written as

$$u(A) - \gamma \cdot T \cdot u(\hat{A}) = -\langle \epsilon \rangle \cdot T \cdot x^{O\hat{E}} \quad (4)$$

where u denote the displacements of equivalent points at a periodic boundary expressed by their coordinate vectors A and \hat{A} , respectively. T is a transformation matrix between adjacent sub-domains, $\langle \epsilon \rangle$ is the volume averaged strain tensor and $\gamma = \pm 1$ describes the load reversal factor. Considering the

rUC shown in Fig. 3, the PBCs can be implemented by enforcing a series of linear constraint equations between displacements of equivalent nodes on the periodic boundary mesh.

2.4 Interpenetration Correction and Compaction

Before the textile can be compacted to the desired FVF, potential volumetric interpenetrations are resolved by means of a fictitious explicit thermal disturbance step. The procedure is highlighted in Fig. 4. Initially, the unit cell is subjected to a decrease in temperature accompanied by volumetric shrinkage of the yarns up to a point where all parts are distinctively separated. While the latter are subsequently reset to their initial temperature, they are now capable of interacting with each other by means of activated contact conditions. Considering the gradual expansion, a smooth transition into a compatible deformed geometric state is achieved. As this is a purely geometrical procedure of contraction and subsequent expansion, the constitutive law implemented is solely fictitious: orthotropic coefficients of thermal expansions (CTEs) eliminate axial stretching, and an elasto-plastic material model allows local yielding at critical contact locations, in particular at the convergence point of axial, positive and negative braid yarn depicted in Fig. 4. Here, the yarns are tightly interlocked, and this clinching effect can give rise to high localised contact stresses.

Figure 4: Resolving interpenetrations (a) initial state (b) separation after contraction (c) interlock after expansion

A key feature of the presented work is the subsequent unit cell compaction step. As opposed to explicitly modelling the forming process using a finite number of fabric layers in combination with a tool, we rely solely on the application of out-of-plane PBCs to further minimise computational effort. A flexible membrane, which implicitly simulates the support of adjacent layers by means of PBCs, is introduced on the top and the bottom of the rUC. With the equivalence framework introduced previously, different nesting conditions, such as ply shifting or flipping can be investigated.

It is important to note that the purpose of the model at this stage is not to represent a dry fabric. All input parameters should be chosen to match the finished composite as closely as possible, since the compaction step's primary mechanism is the distortion and repositioning of yarns within the rUC, such that large resin rich regions are closed. During this operation, all volumes and hence FVFs remain constant, enabling a priori determination of the average compacted ply thickness $\bar{t}_{rUC,c}$ to achieve the global target FVF $\varphi_{F,rUC}$:

$$\bar{t}_{rUC,c} = \frac{V_a \cdot \kappa_a + V_b \cdot \kappa_b}{4 \cdot \varphi_{F,rUC} \cdot h_{rUC} \cdot w_{rUC}} = \frac{h_{rUC} \cdot A_a \cdot \kappa_a + 2 \cdot L_{u'} \cdot A_b \cdot \kappa_b}{2 \cdot \varphi_{F,rUC} \cdot h_{rUC} \cdot w_{rUC}} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{where } w_{rUC} = \frac{s_a}{2} ; h_{rUC} = \frac{s_a}{\tan(\theta)} \quad (6)$$

Figure 5: PBC relations satisfying periodic compatibility

The out-of-plane PBCs for the rUC in its compacted state are displayed in Fig. 5. Considering both the top and bottom unit cell assembled with a rotation of magnitude π about the z-axis, axial yarns of adjacent layers are positioned such that they are capable of closing large initial voids originating from the variable braid thickness. In the case of 'structural nesting' described by Endruweit and Long [13], zones devoid of axial yarns are filled by their respective counterpart in an adjacent layer, which yields a rUC with a locally varying thickness. The identical nesting case can be obtained by incorporating a translational offset of w_{rUC} for the top and bottom rUC. However, a specific set of out-of-plane PBCs may not be chosen arbitrarily. Since rotational and mirror symmetries are exploited simultaneously in \hat{E}_2 and \hat{E}_4 , the top and bottom layers are inversely arranged in order to satisfy the overall compatibility of the periodic structure.

As the overall layer thickness gradually decreases over time, the global fibre volume fraction increases up to its target value. For a $[0/\pm 45]$ braid under investigation, the process is visualized using an assembly of several rUCs in Fig. 6. From the initial state at $\varphi_{F,rUC} = 0.38$, the flat membranes are subjected to a prescribed displacement. Once interacting with the fabric, mutual deformations occur. Upon further compaction, they tend to locally accommodate to the underlying yarn shapes, thus increasing the contact area and the resulting compaction pressure. The final stage features a tightly packed structure of deformed yarns in direct contact. Here, the initially straight axial yarns exhibit a minor degree of crimp, which is accompanied by a reduction in crimp in the braid yarns.

In the last step, a non-conformal tetrahedral matrix mesh is generated through a series of boolean operations. The resulting meshes are coupled using a cohesive contact formulation in order to ensure displacement continuity. After updating the local fibre orientations for the compacted yarns, elastic properties can be readily obtained through the application of principal load cases and subsequent homogenisation.

Figure 6: Evolution of global fibre volume fraction $\varphi_{F,rUC}$ during compaction simulation

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the presented paper, the previously established framework is applied to predict the non-linear mechanical response for a 2×2 $[0/\pm 45]$ triaxial braid manufactured from Toho-Tenax HTS40 F13 12K yarns for both the axial and braid yarns in combination with a Hexcel Hexflow RTM6 epoxy resin. Geometry data was obtained from measurements on undamaged CT data and polished micro-sections and is summarised in Table 1. Results in terms of stress-strain curves will be discussed within the presentation.

Table 1: Geometry data

θ (°)	$\varphi_{F,rUC}$ (-)	κ_a (-)	κ_b (-)	$\bar{t}_{rUC,c}$ (um)	s_a (um)	w_a (um)	t_a (um)	s_b (um)	w_b (um)	t_b (um)
45	0.56	0.64	0.70	751.8	4252	2269	454	3058	2818	308

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